

STRATEGIC HUMAN CAPITAL MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING INDUSTRIES: AN EVALUATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract

Strategic human capital management (SHCM) is considered indispensable in organizations to enhancing value of the business. SHCM is a people focused approach to HR and includes various functions starting from recruitment to employee training, performance management and employee retention. The present study was focused on examining the impact of SHCM practices on organizational effectiveness. The research was done in three large manufacturing industries in Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh, India. Structured questionnaire was framed on various SHCM practices and distributed to employees to collect their responses Employee responses were analyzed through SPSS software for statistical analysis. The main objective of this study is to identify the association between SHCM practices and organizational effectiveness. This study is important for organizations for identifying the need of implementation of SHCM practices for better outcomes. SHCM is considered as essential for all HR related initiatives. The study results revealed that SHCM has a strong impact on organizational effectiveness.

Keywords: Strategic Human Capital Management, Manufacturing Industries, Organizational Effectiveness, Recruitment, Employee Training, Employee Retention, Performance Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Adam Smith was the first person to develop the term human capital in 1776, he argued that the wealth of the nation is different based on the way of working employees with different education level and training reflects the returns. In the concept of HCM employees will be treated as investment and it includes life cycle of managing employees starting from recruitment to retirement. SHCM is a people focused approach and combines with HR initiatives to manage workforce. SHCM helps the management to develop workforce throughout the employee life cycle. SHCM practices includes various activities like manpower planning, recruitment of right candidate, onboarding, career development plan, performance management, compensation planning and employee retention. Organizations are facing significant hurdles in talent acquisition and employee retention in the competitive world. So strategic human capital is essential to face competitiveness and to improve organizational performance. SHC practices are effective on Talent acquisition and employee development. So that Organizations gives priority to SHC practices to employee engagement and higher productivity and also to achieve sustainable competitive advantage. Companies recognizes implementing SHC strategies

fosters growth and innovation and important to achieving strategic goals (Fridaus et al.,2023) Strategic human capital is required to focus on recruitment, Training and organizational culture to enhance employee competencies (Iznillah & Julita, 2024). Organization can leverage skills and knowledge of the employees to drive innovation and adaptability.

Objectives of the study:

1. To assess the association between SHCM practices and organizational effectiveness
2. To identify the SHCM practices implementing in manufacturing industries
3. To examine the impact of SHCM practices on organizational effectiveness
4. To assess the employee job satisfaction on human capital management practices

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Overview of the human capital management

There is an association between human capital, competitive advantage and firm performance therefore it takes a holistic approach in understanding of the role of human capital to create value to the firms. (Ebes Esho¹, 2020). Employee capabilities are based on training and development and job satisfaction level of the employees (Nick Bontis, 2007). Commitment towards human capital is important in organizations to sustained firm performance and found that there is an impact of commitment on human resources (JimAndersén, 2024). knowledge absorptive capacity and innovative capabilities has an influence on business performance (Binh Thi Thanh Truong and Phuong V, 2023) Intellectual capital plays a critical role in influencing the development performance of new products and there is a positive relationship between intellectual capital and organizational learning (Gholamhossein Mehralian, 2024). There is an effect and connection between human capital, sustainable development, economic growth and natural resources (Yu Jie, 2024). The intellectual capital has a significant influence on organizational performance. The six elements of intellectual capital i.e. structural capital, human capital, customer capital, technological capital, social and human capital management has a strong influence on organizational performance (Maryam Jameelah Hashim, 2015).

Human resource attributes have a positive effect of on the overall business performance. The provision of broad services is the key to enhance the competitiveness among the industries and for business performance by industry sectors (Chia-Chi Lee, 2023). Entrepreneurial leadership attributes plays an important role on the organizational effectiveness in the manufacturing sector (Prachee Mishra, 2017). Human capital differs across four employment modes i.e job-based employment, knowledge-based employment, alliance and contract workers (David P. Lepak, 2001). Intellectual capital has positive impact on firm performance of digital platform based MNEs. Human capital is identified as important factor to improve firm performance. (Sheshadri Chatterjee,

2023). Community engagement, training, technology integration and institutional support are essential for human capital development (Aliyu Alhaji Abubakar, 2024). Intellectual capital leads to an increase in the effectiveness of the activities of the organization and also productivity of the organization. Intellectual capital is considered as key development factor in national innovation economy (Larisa Strelnikova, 2022)

2.2 Hypothesis development

The various practices of strategic human capital management were analysed and formulated hypothesis to measure the relationship between SHCM practices and organizational effectiveness. The SHCM practices and its relation with organizational effectiveness are presented below.

2.2.1. The association between Manpower planning and organizational effectiveness (H1)

Shireen fathima 2024 has argued that Strategic manpower planning challenges are helpful to attract and retain talent and to enhance manpower planning and these key variables plays an important role to improve employee performance. Effective manpower planning is essential for optimising employee performance in the organization (Ebele Victoria Ezeneme, 2024)

2.2.2. There is an association between Recruitment and selection and organizational effectiveness (H2)

Marcel van Marrewijk, 2003 argued that to hire the right candidate suitable to the job, organizations need for implement effective recruitment and selection process

2.2.3. There is a positive relationship between Onboarding and organizational effectiveness (H3)

The findings by Brett S. Bowers, 2023 proved that the employees onboarding process plays a significant role on employee job satisfaction, job embeddedness and organizational commitment

2.2.4. There is an association between Compensation policy and organizational effectiveness (H4)

Rewards and compensation practices in the organization has a significant role on employee retention. When the employee has positive perception on HR practices causes on increase in employee retention (Zubair Hassan1, 2022). Research findings by R. Lalitha S. Fernando 2023 states that among the all human resource practices compensation is also one of the effecting variable to achieve organizational objectives and the performance of the organization is depends up on the human resources.

2.2.5. There is an association between Coaching and mentoring and organizational effectiveness (H5)

Mentoring and coaching effects the employee performance and helps to grow the business by development of human capital (Pedro nunez-cacho utrilla, 2012)

2.2.6. Employee training has positive impact on organizational effectiveness (H6)

Nick Bontis, 2007 has argued that employee capabilities are based on effective implementation of training in the organization. Training enhances the skills and knowledge of the employee. Increase in human capital leads to increase in performance in industrial sector (Dr. Ahmed, 2024)

2.2.7. There is an association between competency and career development plan and organizational effectiveness (H7)

Performance appraisals are useful to measure employee skills and organizations identify the additional education or training programs for career development of the employees (Wenny Desty Febrian, 2023). Career development practices are important in emphasising the role in promoting employee satisfaction and for their professional growth (Anusuya M, 2024)

2.2.8. There is a significant positive effect of employee retention on organizational effectiveness. (H8)

Training and development programs, employee assessment and rewarding employees based on performance leads to employee retention so that long term employees are familiar to the company's process which leads to increase the efficiency of the organization (Marcel van Marrewijk , 2003)

3. METHODOLOGY

Both primary and also secondary data were used for the present research study. Primary data was collected through questionnaires and were prepared to represent the impact of SHCM practices on organizational effectiveness. Secondary data was collected through previous research studies and findings on the present topic and also from books and magazines. A structured questionnaire was framed and all the activities of HR starting from man power planning to employee retention were considered for measurement of organizational effectiveness. Manufacturing industries were selected for the research and a total of 535 responses were received from the various employees. Stratified sampling method was applied to collect data and all category employee responses were collected. SPSS software 8.1.1 used for statistical analysis and techniques includes one sample Kolmogorov test, spearman bivariate correlation, Chi square test and ordinal logistic regression analysis were applied to find the results.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Initially one sample Kolmogorov test was applied to test the normality and the following results were found. The test was performed on SHCM practices and we should not accept the null hypothesis if the P value is less than 0.05. Table 1 presents the results of test distribution and it is observed that the test distribution is normal for all SHCM practices.

Table 1: Results of One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

Name of the variable	P value	Result of test distribution
Manpower planning (MP)	<.001	Normal
Recruitment and selection (RS)	<.001	Normal
Onboarding (OB)	<.001	Normal
Compensation policy (CP)	<.001	Normal
Coaching and mentoring (CM)	<.001	Normal
Employee training (ET)	<.001	Normal
Competency and career development plan (CCDP)	<.001	Normal
Employee retention (ER)	<.001	Normal

Spearman bivariate correlation was applied to know whether the two variables are correlated or not. This test was applied to know the correlation between SHCM practices and organizational effectiveness and the results are displayed in the table 2. The results of 535 employee’s response of SHCM practices on organizational effectiveness (OE) was shown below. There was a strong positive correlation between manpower planning and organizational effectiveness (0.57), employee retention and OE (0.167), Recruitment and selection and employee training has weak correlation with OE (0.105) and (0.133), Compensation policy has no correlation with OE (0.063), Onboarding, coaching and mentoring and competency and career development plan has negative correlation with OE (-0.086), (-0.067), (-0.014) respectively. From the test it is concluded that manpower planning and employee retention has positive correlation with organizational effectiveness in manufacturing industries.

Table 2: Results of spearman bivariate correlation

Correlation between variables	Correlation coefficient	Sig.(2 tailed)	Result
Manpower planning and OE	0.57	0.191	Strong Positive correlation and insignificant
Recruitment and selection and OE	0.105	0.016	Weak positive correlation and significant
Onboarding and OE	-0.086	0.046	Negative correlation and significant
Compensation policy and OE	0.063	0.146	No monotonic relationship and insignificant
Coaching and mentoring and OE	-0.067	0.121	Negative correlation and insignificant
Employee training and OE	0.133	0.002	Weak positive correlation and significant
Competency and career development plan and OE	-0.014	0.747	Negative correlation and insignificant
Employee retention and OE	0.167	0.001	Strong Positive correlation and significant

Chi square test was applied to compare the satisfaction level of employees on SHCM practices and its effect on organizational effectiveness. Results of chi square cross tabulation was presented in table no.3. From the results it was analyzed that organizational effectiveness was rating with 3 and 4 and employees responded to various SHCM practices with rating 3 were positively associated with organizational effectiveness with rating 3 and employee responses with rating 4 on SHCM practices were positively associated with organizational effectiveness with rating 4. So, it is observed that if employees are more satisfied with the SHCM practices there is high impact on

organizational effectiveness and if the employees were less satisfied there is less effect on organizational effectiveness.

Table 3: Results of chi square cross tabulation

Organizational effectiveness		Employee satisfaction	MP	RS	OB	CP	CM	ET	CCDP	ER	
		3	Disagree (2)	26	0	0	9	0	13	21	31
			Neutral (3)	110	90	136	60	136	110	106	105
			Agree (4)	0	46	0	67	0	13	9	0
			Strongly agree (5)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		4	Disagree (2)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			Neutral (3)	153	0	67	0	5	0	82	33
			Agree (4)	168	161	245	225	363	302	255	240
			Strongly agree (5)	78	238	87	175	31	97	62	126
		Total (N)		535	535	535	535	535	535	535	535

From the Table 4, chi square test values and symmetric measures are showed and the observations from the test is that there is a strong association between SHCM practices and organizational effectiveness. So, it accepts alternative hypothesis and rejects null hypothesis. Here all the chi-square test values on SHCM practices are high and P value is less than 0.005.

Table 4: Results of Chi square test values and symmetric measures

Variable	Pearson chi square	P value	Phi Cramer's	Result	Decision
Manpower planning	197.461	<.001	.608	Strong association between variables are measured	Reject the null hypothesis
Recruitment and selection	346.284	<.001	.805	Strong association between variables are measured	Reject the null hypothesis
Onboarding	298.237	<.001	.747	Strong association between variables are measured	Reject the null hypothesis
Compensation policy	262.964	<.001	.701	Strong association between variables are measured	Reject the null hypothesis
Coaching and mentoring	509.562	<.001	.976	Strong association between variables are measured	Reject the null hypothesis
Employee training	469.259	<.001	.937	Strong association between variables are measured	Reject the null hypothesis
Competency and career development plan	492.223	<.001	.959	Strong association between variables are measured	Reject the null hypothesis
Employee retention	402.560	<.001	.867	Strong association between variables are measured	Reject the null hypothesis

Further an ordinal logistic regression analysis was applied to determine reason-result relationship between eight independent variables: manpower planning, Recruitment and selection, onboarding, compensation policy, Coaching and mentoring, Employee training, Competency and career development plan, Employee retention and dependent variable: organizational effectiveness. From the result it is observed that there is a significant effect of SHCM practices on organizational effectiveness.

Table 5: Result of ordinal logistic regression analysis

Model fitting information		Goodness of fit		Pseudo R-square	
Chi-square	226.554	Chi-square	420.937 (pearson)	Cox and snell	.345
Sig	<.001		348.493 (Deviance)	Nagelkerke	.509
		Sig.	.934(pearson)	McFadden	.373
			1.000(Deviance)		
Decision	Good model fit		Good model fit		There was 37.3% improvement on organizational effectiveness.

From the above table model fitting information is given. Here the significance value is less than 0.001. So that there is a significant improvement in the fit and the model is considered a good fit. We can see here there is a significant improvement in the model over the null model.

Here the goodness of fit statistics indicates adequately fits when significance value is greater than 0.05. Non-significant test results indicate good fit the data (Petrucci, 2009, Field 2018) so here the goodness of fit value is more than 0.05, it indicates the observed data is corresponding to the assumed data. In this analysis Pearson chi square test value was ($\chi^2(466) = 420.937, P=.934$) and Deviance test value was ($\chi^2(466) = 348.493, P=1.000$). Both were insignificant and indicates test result was good model fit.

McFadden value of R square was 0.373. Mc Fadden (1979) recommends the values between .2 to .4 considered as good model fit. There was 37.3% improvement in the prediction of outcome based on predictors when compared to null model. It is considered that when organizations implement SCHM practices in manufacturing industries there was 37.3% improvement on organizational effectiveness was identified.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The research findings by Attia Aman-Ullaha, 2022, Human capital is essential for organizational progress. Research findings showed that there is a positive association between attributes of human capital and organizational performance. Some important contribution by Christian Ax, 2008, proved that even though not reflected in actual disclosure there is a significant association between human capital management practices and human capital disclosure.

Employee recruitment, training, career and compensation planning have an impact on organizational performance. So, it is strong evidence to accept hypothesis H2, H4, H6 and H7. Effective workforce planning, development and continuous improvement is required for organizational success (Awol Hussien Aman, 2023). It is considered to be evident to accept H1.

Effective onboarding process enhances work engagement and organizational commitment among new employees (Francisco Cesário, 2019). Onboarding process is crucial for effective human capital management practices. So, the hypothesis H3 is accepted.

Investment in talent management, education and recognition enhances the employee satisfaction and employee retention. (Unnar Theodorsson, 2023). This contribution supports to accept hypothesis H8.

Coaching and mentoring is an effective human capital management practice and that promotes workplace diversity, develops employee talent and improves employee satisfaction (Heather Getha, 2006).

There is an association between coaching and mentoring process and organizational effectiveness. So, H5 is considered to be accepted. Human capital is considered as strategic asset and it contributes organizational effectiveness. There is a strategic importance of human capital (Abraham Carmeli, 2004). Work engagement plays a crucial role in mediating the impact of human capital management practices on employee performance.

Employee training, career planning and rewards for the employee performance were positively related to employee engagement (Njanjobea Isah Leontes, 2024). So, this contribution helps to accept the hypothesis H3, H6 and H7.

In conclusion the research results explored the critical role of SHCM practices in enhancing organizational effectiveness in manufacturing industries and is considered to be an important element to foster the growth of the industries.

6. LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The present study is depends on the data collected from three large manufacturing industries in Andhra Pradesh, India. So, further the study can be extended to other states in India.

The present research findings suggested that manufacturing industries need to implement SHCM practices to improve organizational effectiveness. The present research study proved that there is only 37.3% improvement on organizational effectiveness by the implementation of SHCM practices.

Research contribution by Hadi Teimour, 2018 identified that when there is increase in the existing challenges in organizational strategies there is decrease in the effectiveness of human capital management practices. It means existing challenges will impact the effectiveness of the human capital management practices. So, the organizations need to face the current challenges by find the gap between current management practices and desired outcome.

HCM is considered to be critical issue across the globe. In India organizations faces difficult to find the right talent, recruit and retain the employees (R.Raghavan, 2011). The present study recommends the company's management to implement HCM strategies effectively, further these are helpful to recruit the right talent, performance management and also for employee retention.

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